

Some 3-arylimino-5-(isopropylidene hydrazono-N)-1,2,4-dithiazolidines : Oxidative Debenzylation of 1-(isopropylideneamino)-5-aryl-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets

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The synthesis of 3-arylimino-5-(isopropylidenehydrazono-N)-1,2,4-dithiazolidines has been described by the oxidative debenylation of the corresponding 1-(isopropylideneamino)-5-aryl-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets. These compounds have been characterized by the direct oxidation of the corresponding 2,4-dithiobiurets and also by i.r. spectra.

THE success of our investigations in the synthesis of 3,5-disubstitutedimino-1,2,4-dithiazolidines through the oxidative dealkylation and cyclisation of the corresponding 1,5-disubstituted-2-S-alkyliso-4-thiobiurets¹⁻⁶ has convinced us about the feasibility of extending this reaction to the synthesis of some, hitherto, unknown 1,5-disubstituted-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets and their conversion to 3-arylimino-5-(isopropylidenehydrazono-N)-1,2,4-dithiazolidines.

This communication describes the synthesis of certain new 3-arylimino-5-(isopropylidenehydrazono-N)-1,2,4-dithiazolidines by the oxidative debenylation and ring closure of the related

1-(isopropylideneamino)-5-aryl-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets.

Acetonethiosemicarbazone(I) was benzylated with benzylchloride in ethanol in presence of sodium ethoxide, and resulting S-benzyliso-acetonethiosemicarbazone(II) was condensed with appropriate arylisothiocyanate to afford 1-(isopropylideneamino)-5-aryl-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets(III). The chloroform solution of the latter was then treated with bromine, when the benzyl group of these was eliminated as benzyl bromide followed by ring closure to the related 3-arylimino-5-(isopropylidenehydrazono-N)-1,2,4-dithiazolidines(V). These have also been obtained by the oxidation of the related

Where : Ar = Phenyl-, o-tolyl-, p-tolyl-, o-chlorophenyl-, p-chlorophenyl-, o-methoxyphenyl-, p-methoxyphenyl-, m-ethoxyphenyl.

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1-(isopropylideneamino)-5-aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets(IV), which were obtained by the reductive debenzoylation of the related isodithiobiurets(III) with hydrogen sulphide in pyridine-triethylamine and also by the reduction of (V) under identical conditions. In all the cases, the structures of the compounds (IV) and (V) were confirmed by their synthesis through alternative routes as described above and also by mixed melting point technique and identical i.r. spectra.

The reactions have been represented :

Experimental

Melting points were determined by Kofler hot stage apparatus and are uncorrected.

TABLE 1—SYNTHESIS OF 1-(ISOPROPYLIDENEAMINO)-5-ARYL-2-S-BENZYLISO-4-THIOBIURETS(III)

Acetone-S-benzyl-isothiosemi-carbazone	Isothio-cyanates	1-(Isopropylidene-amino)-5-aryl-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets formed (Molecular formula)	m.p. °C	Yield
Acetone-S-benzyl-isothio-	Phenyl-	1-(Isopropylidene-amino)-5-phenyl-(C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₄ S ₂)	215	62
Acetone-S-benzyl-isothio-	<i>o</i> -Tolyl-	1-(Isopropylidene-amino)-5- <i>o</i> -tolyl-(C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₄ S ₂)	92	78
Acetone-S-benzyl-isothio-	<i>p</i> -Tolyl-	1-(Isopropylidene-amino)-5- <i>p</i> -tolyl-(C ₁₈ H ₂₀ N ₄ S ₂)	146	80
Acetone-S-benzyl-isothio-	<i>o</i> -Chloro-phenyl-	1-(Isopropylidene-amino)-5- <i>o</i> -chloro-phenyl-(C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₄ S ₂ Cl)	182	70
Acetone-S-benzyl-isothio-	<i>p</i> -Chloro-phenyl-	1-(Isopropylidene-amino)-5- <i>p</i> -chloro-phenyl-(C ₁₈ H ₁₇ N ₄ S ₂ Cl)	185	85
Acetone-S-benzyl-isothio-	<i>o</i> -Methoxy-phenyl-	1-(Isopropylidene-amino)-5- <i>o</i> -methoxy-phenyl-(C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₄ S ₂ O)	180	82
Acetone-S-benzyl-isothio-	<i>p</i> -Methoxy-phenyl-	1-(Isopropylidene-amino)-5- <i>p</i> -methoxy-phenyl-(C ₁₉ H ₂₂ N ₄ S ₂ O)	161	82
Acetone-S-benzyl-isothio-	<i>p</i> -Ethoxy-phenyl-	1-(Isopropylidene-amino)-5- <i>p</i> -ethoxy-phenyl-(C ₂₀ H ₂₆ N ₄ S ₂ O)	182	85

Typical i.r. frequencies (cm⁻¹) of 1-(isopropylideneamino)-5-phenyl-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiuret : 3200m, N-H stretching ; 1120, 1145 ν s, 1200 w, N-C-N grouping, 1590 w, N-C=N-

grouping.

All the compounds gave consistent C, H and N analyses.

Acetone thiosemicarbazone(I) was prepared by the known procedure⁷ and its S-benzyl derivative (II) was obtained by benzylation with benzyl chloride in presence of sodium ethoxide⁸.

1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5-aryl-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets(III) :

The details of a typical experiment are as follows :

Benzene solution of S-benzyliso acetone thiosemicarbazone (2.21 g) was refluxed with phenylisothiocyanate (1.35 g) for 1 hr. On evaporation of the solvent, 1-(isopropylideneamino)-5-phenyl-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiuret was obtained as a semisolid which on washing with petroleum ether and addition of a little ethanol became crystalline. It was crystallized from ethanol, m.p. 215° (yield 2.6 g, 70%). The results of these experiments are summarized in Table 1.

3-Arylimino-5-(isopropylidenehydrazono-N)-1,2,4-dithiazolidines(V) :

(i) Oxidative debenzoylation of 1-(isopropylideneamino)-5-aryl-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets :

The substituted 2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiuret made into a paste with a little chloroform or carbon tetrachloride was treated with liquid bromine until the colour of bromine persisted. The reaction mixture warmed up considerably evolving lachrymatory fumes of benzyl bromide. After 30 min, the semisolid product was washed first with ether and then with a mixture of ether and little ethanol, when the hydrobromide of the oxidation product separated out as a crystalline mass. On treatment with ammonia the free base was obtained, which was thoroughly washed with ether, and crystallized from ethanol. The dithiazolidine bases thus obtained showed no depression in m.p. when mixed with the authentic samples obtained by the oxidation of the corresponding 1,5-disubstituted-2,4-dithiobiurets.

(ii) Oxidation of 1-(isopropylideneamino)-5-aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets(IV) with bromine in ethanol :

The 1-(isopropylideneamino)-5-aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets listed in Table 3 were oxidized with bromine in dilute ethanolic solution and ether added when the hydrobromide of the respective 3-arylimino-5-(isopropylidenehydrazono-N)-1,2,4-dithiazolidine precipitated. Free bases were obtained by treating these with ammonia and crystallized from ethanol (Table 2).

1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5-aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets (IV) :

(i) Reductive debenzoylation of 1-(isopropylideneamino)-5-aryl-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets(III) :

TABLE 2—3-ARYLIMINO-5-(ISOPROPYLIDENEHYDRAZONO-N)-1,2,4-DITHIAZOLIDINES(V) : OXIDATIVE DEBENZYLATION OF 1-(ISOPROPYLIDENEAMINO)-5-ARYL-2-S-BENZYLISO-4-THIOBIURETS(III) WITH LIQUID BROMINE IN CHLOROFORM

1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5-aryl-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets : oxidized	3-Arylimino-5-(isopropylidenehydrazono-N)-1,2,4-dithiazolidines : formed (Molecular formula)	m.p. °C	Yield %
1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5-phenyl-	3-phenylimino-5-(isopropylidenehydrazono-N)- (C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₄ S ₂)	135	70
1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5- <i>o</i> -tolyl-	3- <i>o</i> -tolylimino-5-(isopropylidenehydrazono-N)- (C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ S ₂)	160	75
1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5- <i>p</i> -tolyl-	3- <i>p</i> -tolylimino-5-(isopropylidenehydrazono-N)- (C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ S ₂)	154	85
1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5- <i>o</i> -chlorophenyl-	3- <i>o</i> -chlorophenylimino-5-(isopropylidenehydrazono-N)- (C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ S ₂ Cl)	181	72
1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-	3- <i>p</i> -chlorophenylimino-5-(isopropylidenehydrazono-N)- (C ₁₁ H ₁₁ N ₄ S ₂ Cl)	138	90
1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5- <i>o</i> -methoxyphenyl-	3- <i>o</i> -methoxyphenylimino-5-(isopropylidenehydrazono-N)- (C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ S ₂ O)	172	60
1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5- <i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl-	3- <i>p</i> -methoxyphenylimino-5-(isopropylidenehydrazono-N)- (C ₁₂ H ₁₄ N ₄ S ₂ O)	164	65
1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5- <i>p</i> -ethoxyphenyl-	3- <i>p</i> -ethoxyphenylimino-5-(isopropylidenehydrazono-N)- (C ₁₃ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₂ O)	152	70

Typical i.r. frequencies (cm⁻¹) of 3-phenylimino-5-(isopropylidenehydrazono-N)-1,2,4-dithiazolidine: C=N 1620 s; ring-S-S-linkage 480 s; 3200m, N-H stretching.

All the compounds gave consistent C, H and N analyses.

The desired isodithiobiuret(III) was dissolved in pyridinetriethylamine (6 : 1) solution and a stream of dry hydrogen sulphide passed for 3 hrs. The resulting solution on filtration, cooling and neutralization with dilute hydrochloric acid afforded the expected dithiobiuret(IV). These were crystallized from ethanol (Table 3).

(ii) Reduction of 3-arylimino-5-(isopropylidenehydrazono-N)-1,2,4-dithiazolidines(V) by ethanolic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide :

The dithiazolidines were dissolved in hot ethanolic ammoniacal hydrogen sulphide solution and a stream of hydrogen sulphide passed for 3 hrs. The clear solution on dilution with water or acidification

TABLE 3—SYNTHESIS OF 1-(ISOPROPYLIDENEAMINO)-5-ARYL-2,4-DITHIOBIURETS(IV) BY REDUCTIVE DEBENZYLATION OF 1-(ISOPROPYLIDENEAMINO)-5-ARYL-2-S-BENZYLISO-4-THIOBIURETS(III) WITH HYDROGEN SULPHIDE IN PYRIDINE-TRIETHYLAMINE

1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5-aryl-2-S-benzyliso-4-thiobiurets : reduced	1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5-aryl-2,4-dithiobiurets : formed (Molecular formula)	m.p. °C	Yield %
1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5-phenyl-	1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5-phenyl- (C ₁₁ H ₁₄ N ₄ S ₂)	163	60
1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5- <i>o</i> -tolyl-	1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5- <i>o</i> -tolyl- (C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₂)	115	72
1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5- <i>p</i> -tolyl-	1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5- <i>p</i> -tolyl- (C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₂)	127	78
1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5- <i>o</i> -chlorophenyl-	1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5- <i>o</i> -chlorophenyl- (C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₄ S ₂ Cl)	138	70
1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl-	1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5- <i>p</i> -chlorophenyl- (C ₁₁ H ₁₂ N ₄ S ₂ Cl)	152	80
1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5- <i>o</i> -methoxyphenyl-	1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5- <i>o</i> -methoxyphenyl- (C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₂ O)	145	75
1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5- <i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl-	1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5- <i>p</i> -methoxyphenyl- (C ₁₂ H ₁₆ N ₄ S ₂ O)	125	75
1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5- <i>p</i> -ethoxyphenyl-	1-(Isopropylideneamino)-5- <i>p</i> -ethoxyphenyl- (C ₁₃ H ₁₈ N ₄ S ₂ O)	140	70

Typical i.r. frequencies (cm⁻¹) of 1-(isopropylideneamino)-5-phenyl-2,4-dithiobiuret : 3395 w, N-H stretching, 1150 m, shows N-C-N grouping; 1620 s, C=N grouping.

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All the compounds gave consistent C, H and N analyses.

afforded the related dithiobiurets. These were crystallized from ethanol.

The identity of each product was established by mixed m.p. technique with the authentic sample obtained by conventional reduction of the isodithiobiurets described in Table 3 and by identical i.r. spectra.

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